

Postoperative pain management after craniotomy: Literature review and evaluation of evidence

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ABSTRACT Background: The effective management of postoperative pain tends to reduce morbidity and mortality. Currently, it is becoming clear that appropriate and adequate analgesia is a significant component of post-craniotomy care. The goal of this review is to analyse and appraise the evidence for postoperative analgesia following craniotomy. **Methods:** A literature search conducted using EMBASE, Medline and Cochrane database for systematic reviews. Keywords applied were “postoperative analgesia”, “neurosurgery”, “neurosurgical procedures”. Resultant yield limited to 10 years, English language journal, intracranial (craniotomy) surgeries. Studies were limited to English and those involving humans. Studies limited from 1995 to 2016. Relevant studies were isolated for further critique. About 30 trials were identified, but some could not be retrieved. **Results:** Total of 140 citations was identified after thorough screening non-relevant studies, and non-randomised clinical trials were exempted. One systematic review and three randomised controlled study, Studies were limited to English and those involving humans. **Conclusion:** The data available showed improved analgesia with use of codeine sulphate against the backdrop of the popular tramadol which is a weak opioid fraught with significant post-operative nausea and vomiting. Also, some evidence supports the use of regional scalp block for post craniotomy analgesia. The non-narcotics paracetamol and NSAIDs such Ketoprofen are useful analgesia compliments

KEYWORDS postoperative pain, analgesia, craniotomy, opioids

INTRODUCTION

A craniotomy is a common operative procedure in Neurosurgery involving creating an adequate opening in the cranium or skull for optimum access to intracranial contents. A craniotomy may be infratentorial or supratentorial, or combination of both, infratentorial craniotomy is also called skull base. It is believed that the brain lack pain sensation, most of the pain innervations is limited to the meningeal covering or extracranial muscles and fascia [1]. This concept of the insensate brain has led to

the widespread belief of minimum craniotomy pain hence less analgesia needed. Currently, it is becoming clear that appropriate and adequate analgesia is a significant component of post-craniotomy care, though opinion varies regarding suitable analgesia [2]

The effective management of postoperative pain tends to reduce morbidity and mortality. According to International Association for the Study of Pain (I.A.S.P), Pain is an unpleasant sensory and emotional experience associated with existing or potential tissue injury. Postoperative pain is most severe during the first 72 hours following surgery and is usually of limited time frame mostly. Post-craniotomy pains have been shown to have negative effects, ineffective treatment of pain will cause raised sympathetic activity and an increase in systemic blood pressure [3].

An influential study by Stoneham and Walters [4] revealed that almost nine out of ten neuro-anaesthetists surveyed were using codeine sulphate, a weak opioid as first-line analgesia post craniotomy. However, in up to 50% patients it provides inadequate pain relief. Hence the use of codeine has been ques-

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tioned. Eckhardt et al. [5] reported adverse events including sedation, nausea, blurred vision and pruritus were more associated to use of codeine that uses a placebo and more common than morphine.

The goal of this review is to analyse and appraise the evidence for postoperative analgesia following craniotomy.

METHODOLOGY

A comprehensive literature search performed to establish a pool of evidence for informed and evidence-based discussion. A current literature search conducted using EMBASE, Medline and Cochrane database for systematic reviews. Keywords applied were "postoperative analgesia", "neurosurgery", "neurosurgical procedures". Resultant yield limited to 10 years, English language journal, intracranial (craniotomy) surgeries. Studies were limited to English and those involving humans. Studies limited from 1990 to 2016. Relevant studies were isolated for further critique. About 30 trials were identified, but some could not be retrieved. After further critical and rigorous literature search, three randomised controlled trials and one systematic review were appraisals for evaluation of current evidence of analgesia use post-craniotomy.

RESULTS

Total of 140 citations was identified after thorough screening non-relevant studies, and non-randomised clinical trials were exempted. One systematic review and three randomised controlled study, Studies were limited to English and those involving humans.

DISCUSSION

Guilfoyle et al. [10] carried out a systematic review and meta-analysis regional scalp block for post craniotomy analgesia. Inclusion criteria were single or double-blinded randomised controlled trials(RCTs) comparing pre or post regional scalp block(RSB) against no intervention, systemic analgesia or other local intervention in adults undergoing craniotomy with at least one patient reported pain score as an outcome measure. Regional scalp block is any technique where the region of the scalp to be operated on was blocked by injection of local anaesthesia around major innervating sensory nerves [8]. Studies excluded were those solely examining the efficacy of infiltrating local anaesthesia along the planned scalp incision (or postoperatively into the wound margin) as this was not considered a genuine regional block, also studies reporting only physiological variables as outcomes like heart rate or arterial blood pressure without adequate assessment of patient's pain scores were excluded too.

A total of 20 full texts literature were retrieved. In its final search, seven distinct RCTs for supratentorial regional scalp block were finally included in the study with a total number of 325 patients. All included trials were randomised however meta-analysis was performed separately for pain scored assessed. Six studies reported inadequate information regarding the amount of opioids either enteral or parenteral consumption in the immediate postoperative period (24 hours). Meta-analysis showed an overall decrease in opioid requirement associated with regional scalp block, n=6 studies; pooled SMD, -7.09; 95% CI, -1.55 to -0.33; P=0.04; I2=86%. Heterogeneity was significant. Also of significant note, there was no incidence of infections, hematoma, neurapraxia or any other complications associated with regional scalp block in 170 patients involved. The meta-analysis did show that regional scalp block is effective in reducing pain after craniotomy.

Apart from the drawback of small sample size in this study, the efficacy of regional scalp block is adequately significant for analgesia after craniotomy. This procedure is said to be cost-effective, safe and also reliable means of postoperative analgesia after craniotomy procedures. In conclusion, this review confirms the need for a change in practice to regional scalp block for postoperative analgesia post craniotomy.

Hyo-Seok et al. [11] performed a randomised controlled trial to evaluate the efficacy of intravenous patient-controlled analgesia to manage postoperative pain in patients undergoing a craniotomy. Patients were randomised to two groups using sealed envelope method. The results section showed 112 patients consented to participate, five excluded in post-operative period because of ventilatory problems. Two groups compared IV-PCA group (group P) and intermittent analgesic drug injection group (group N). The group sizes are unjustified because for a study to deliver statistically adequate result a sample calculation has to be performed and accordingly substantiated there was no group size calculation, and this is subject to type two errors.

The authors feel this study proved that IV-PCA with fentanyl and ketorolac could provide superior analgesia in craniotomy patients without significant adverse events on any disturbances on neurological examination despite the shortcomings of this study Jones et al. [6] performed a prospective, double-blind, randomised, placebo-controlled study on Parecoxib for analgesia after craniotomy. The authors described the rationale of this study "as to evaluate the analgesic benefit after craniotomy of a single intraoperative dose of parecoxib". They believed that pain after craniotomy is often undertreated and regarding the

choice of analgesia. They concur that opiates carry disadvantages, non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs have antiplatelet actions with a significant risk of bleeding, but COX 2 inhibitors have no risk of bleeding hence the use of parecoxib in this study. This study is of limited value as it addresses the use of parecoxib for pain relief after craniotomy, this is not a popular drug, and its role as an analgesic in the neurosurgical procedure is unclear. The randomisation process was through a computer-generated permutation where patients were allocated to specific group either to receive parecoxib 40mg or saline (placebo) at the closure of the dura. Patients, anaesthetists and investigators were blinded to the content in the syringe for supposed postoperative analgesia; it was labelled "study content". Overall 82 patients were enrolled in this study; two were excluded because craniotomy was not performed. In their study, Parecoxib was found to reduce pain score at six hours and morphine use at 6 and 12 h after operation. Overall it only had minimal impact on postoperative pain. They concluded that only limited evidence was available to justify the use of Parecoxib as an analgesic after craniotomy. The population sampled is too small to change practice. Jeffery et al. [12] explored the comparison of codeine and tramadol in a randomised double-blind prospective study of postoperative analgesia in intracranial surgery, 75 patients undergoing intracranial surgery were sampled especially those with Glasgow coma scale (GCS) score of 15/15 and anticipated to be fully conscious after surgery were included in the study. Exclusion criteria include weight less than 50kg or more than 100kg. It is a double-blinded randomised prospective study; patients were numbered sequentially and allocated randomly using the closed enveloped technique. The identity of the drug given was unknown to both nursing and medical staff. Group 1 received codeine phosphate 60mg; group 2 received tramadol 50mg and 75mg tramadol for group 3 intramuscular route after surgery. There was no significant difference in VAS scores at 24 hours between the three groups ($P=0.096$). There was no significant difference in pain scores between those who underwent an infratentorial and supratentorial craniotomy. Multiple regression analysis confirmed a negative relationship between age and pain that is older patient had lower pain score ($P<0.0001$). Also, postoperative nausea and vomiting were more common in group 3 (tramadol 75mg) ($P<0.0001$). This same set of patients required more additional escape antiemetic than other groups ($P<0.0001$).

The results here are surprisingly not in line with other literature, in this study, codeine provided superior pain relief; postoperative pain score of patients receiving codeine was consistently lower than in those patients receiving either dose of tramadol. Also, the codeine group require fewer injections, larger doses of tramadol seems to have an anti-analgesic effect. The poor results with tramadol 75mg are not consistent with literature findings of potency comparable to 100mg pethidine [9]. Also, tramadol was believed to have potential advantages over all opioids by having weak opioids effects thus avoiding most other the side effects of opioids [9]. This study demonstrates that codeine provides better postoperative pain relief than tramadol.

CONCLUSION

The evidence is very limited, weaknesses in methodology confound most data, and most of the studies have small sample sizes. Large trials on safety and efficacy of analgesia post craniotomy using standardised and widely accepted tools are yet to be performed. The data available showed improved analgesia

with use of codeine sulphate against the backdrop of the popular tramadol which is a weak opioid fraught with significant postoperative nausea and vomiting. Also, some evidence supports the use of regional scalp block for post craniotomy analgesia. The non-narcotics paracetamol and NSAIDs such Ketoprofen are useful analgesia compliments. Also use of a laxative is suggested for corresponding opioid analgesia to prevent constipation and straining worsening pain.

Authors' Statements

Competing Interests

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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